

**PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF CAREER GUIDANCE DURING
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Annotation: In this article psychological problems of career guidance during adolescence were discussed. Furthermore, basic theoretical models of the decision making process were noted.

Key words: *social changes, psychological well-being, social exclusion, discrimination, supportive environments, mental health.*

One in six people are aged 10–19 years. Adolescence is a unique and formative time. Physical, emotional and social changes, including exposure to poverty, abuse, or violence, can make adolescents vulnerable to mental health problems. Protecting adolescents from adversity, promoting socio-emotional learning and psychological well-being, and ensuring access to mental health care are critical for their health and well-being during adolescence and adulthood. Globally, it is estimated that 1 in 7 (14%) 10–19 year-olds experience mental health conditions (1), yet these remain largely unrecognized and untreated. Adolescents with mental health conditions are particularly vulnerable to social exclusion, discrimination, stigma (affecting readiness to seek help), educational difficulties, risk-taking behaviours, physical ill-health and human rights violations.

Adolescence is a crucial period for developing social and emotional habits important for mental well-being. These include adopting healthy sleep patterns; exercising regularly; developing coping, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills; and learning to manage emotions. Protective and supportive environments in the family, at school and in the wider community are important. Multiple factors affect mental health. The more risk factors adolescents are exposed to, the greater the potential impact on their mental health. Factors that can contribute to stress during adolescence include exposure to adversity, pressure to conform with peers and exploration of identity. Media influence and gender norms can exacerbate the disparity between

an adolescent's lived reality and their perceptions or aspirations for the future. Other important determinants include the quality of their home life and relationships with peers. Violence (especially sexual violence and bullying), harsh parenting and severe and socioeconomic problems are recognized risks to mental health[1].

Some adolescents are at greater risk of mental health conditions due to their living conditions, stigma, discrimination or exclusion, or lack of access to quality support and services. These include adolescents living in humanitarian and fragile settings; adolescents with chronic illness, autism spectrum disorder, an intellectual disability or other neurological condition; pregnant adolescents, adolescent parents, or those in early or forced marriages; orphans; and adolescents from minority ethnic or sexual backgrounds or other discriminated groups. Making satisfying career choices can be seen as the development of strong and adaptive vocational commitments, and thus as an important aspect of identity development. It is also a difficult task: many late adolescents struggle with it. Career choice problems can be seen as a manifestation of problematic identity development and more specifically, as problems in commitment formation in the domain of vocational identity. Exploration and commitment formation are seen as two crucial dimensions in identity development. By exploration we mean that individuals are seriously considering different possibilities before they form commitments. Commitment formation refers to the process of making choices in which individuals are personally involved, thus choices about issues that really matters to them. Optimally, identity development proceeds from an initial state in which there are either no commitments or commitments that are adopted from significant others. A career choice is satisfying and adaptive if the choice represents a match between characteristics of the person and of the study or career, and if the person can integrate his or her choice in his overall identity. This implies that also personal and global commitment development are relevant aspects in career choice development. Therefore, we will use vocational, personal and global commitment development as indicators of career choice development[2].

"Career" being a controversial and complex term had been defined by different authors pertaining to their different fields of study and perceptions. Making the right career choice that would keep adolescents relevant in the scheme of activities in the society could be daunting and difficult. Adolescents in our society are often preoccupied with so many thoughts of future career prospects. This, more often than not, often predispose these adolescents to irrational thoughts.

Such irrational thoughts could be debilitating to the society and psychological well-being of adolescents. Transition from secondary school to workplace, college or university is a critical path through which every adolescent must pass through. However, it is not uncommon to aver that many of these adolescents are left unguarded while transiting from college to workplace. Most often, parents, teachers, and friends have encouraged secondary school students to proceed to the university while a good number of secondary school students may end up attending universities without knowing why or what they intend to study of which in most cases career psychologist is needed to ascertain the uncertain issue and finding a helping solution to it. For many, this is an important time for career-related matters that will be beneficial to them. As they face the need to choose an academic major, as well as to develop career goals for the future, career problems often become a developmental phase they must pass through in making proper career choices for life[3].

Starting from various theoretical models of the decision making process and from taxonomies of career choosing problems, they have conceptualized the process of choosing among adolescents as a decision-making process with a number of tasks. First, young persons have to be aware of the necessity of making a choice, then they have to be motivated to make a decision (task: orientation on choice). In our protocol we focus on the awareness and motivation especially in the intake. We check whether it was the adolescent's own choice to enroll. If not, the intake was focused on exploration of the choice situation and the adolescents' feelings about that. For enrollment in the guidance, awareness and some motivation were prerequisite. Then there is the third task of self exploration, consisting in collecting information about themselves and a broad exploration of their context. This means the young person is asked to collect information on the various alternatives that may be chosen. The first sessions in the protocol focus on this task. By means of specific home-assignments the participants were asked to study websites of different universities or colleges, to list the studies that were described there, and to make a list of studies that attracted them and studies that they did not like at all. During the sessions, we discussed their lists, and stimulate them to become more specific, to compare studies and formulate differences etcetera. In the same way, they had to make lists of their own broad job preferences such as, is it important for you to work with people, to help people, to build something). When from this breadth orientation a number of possible courses of study have been chosen, the next assignment follows: in-depth orientation. This task was the focus of the second part of the protocol. The assignments in this part concern searching for more information

on the remaining courses[4]. The participant was stimulated to contact the university, to talk to other students, to study the list of topics in the different courses, etc.

To sum up, all given facts above, career indecision is one of the key aspects that professionals in career guidance counselling are interested in assessing. By analysing various aspects of career indecision this study was able to assess how the case of a career guidance counsellor impacted various difficulties in the career decision-making process of late adolescents. The level of career indecision experienced by the adolescents who received career guidance counselling diminished from time one to time two. This study found empirical evidence to support the notion that late adolescents who receive career guidance counselling are more likely to experience a reduction in their level of career indecision than adolescents who do not receive any form of career guidance counselling intervention.

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